

DepressionControlApp - Reference List

1. WHO Fact-Sheet: Depression, 2023 - World Health Organization (WHO)
2. Jo et al., JMIR mHealth, 2024 - Digital phenotyping review (JMIR mHealth and uHealth)
3. Liu et al., Psychiatry Research, 2024 - HRV & depression severity (PubMed)
4. Liu et al., npj Digital Medicine, 2024 - Passive sensing & suicide meta-analysis (Nature)
5. Myin-Germeys & Kuppens, EMA in Depression, 2015 (PMC)
6. Charoensukmongkol et al., JMIR Serious Games, 2023 - Gamified CBT (JSG)
7. Fraser et al., Nature Biotechnology commentary, 2024 - AI antidepressant prediction (National Elf Service; Time)
8. Wilson et al., Frontiers in Digital Health, 2025 - Clinician dashboards for social data (PMC)
9. Abbar et al., Information, 2024 - Multimodal fusion depression detection (MDPI)
10. WHO Digital Health Classification v2, 2023 - World Health Organization (WHO)